

BLT Dataset: acquisition of the agricultural multimodal Bacchus Long-Term Dataset with automated robot deployment

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Achieving a robust long-term deployment with mobile robots in the agriculture domain is both a demanded and challenging task. The possibility to have autonomous platforms in the field performing repetitive tasks, such as monitoring or harvesting crops, collides with the difficulties posed by the always-changing appearance of the environment due to seasonality. With this scope in mind, we report an ongoing effort in the long-term deployment of an autonomous mobile robot in a vineyard, with the main objective of acquiring what we called the Bacchus Long-Term (BLT) Dataset. This dataset consists of multiple sessions recorded in the same area of a vineyard but at different points in time, covering a total of 7 months to capture the whole canopy growth from March until September. The multimodal dataset recorded is acquired with the main focus put on pushing the develop-

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ment and evaluations of different mapping and localisation algorithms for long-term autonomous robots operation in the agricultural domain. Hence, besides the dataset, we also present an initial study in long-term localisation using four different sessions belonging to four different months with different plant stages. We identify that state-of-the-art localisation methods can only cope partially with the amount of change in the environment, making the proposed dataset suitable to establish a benchmark on which the robotics community can test its methods. On our side, we anticipate two solutions pointed at extracting stable temporal features for improving long-term 4d localisation results. The BLT dataset is available at Incn.ac/lcas-blt.

KEYWORDS

Dataset, Long-term, Agriculture, Mobile robots, Autonomous navigation, Field robotics, Robot localisation

1 | INTRODUCTION

Agricultural environments, such as orchards or vineyards, offer many challenges for autonomously and safely deploying robots at work (Duckett et al., 2018). For example, the authors in Hroob et al. (2021) compared state-of-the-art simultaneous localisation and mapping (SLAM) methods in a simulated vineyard environment and found that plants changing appearance can lead to a degradation of the localisation module, with the robot drifting from its course. The main reason why existing SLAM methods fail in guaranteeing robust and long-term performances in the agriculture domain is that they are developed and evaluated mainly in urban or indoor environments, which are consistent across time (Labbé and Michaud, 2019) or present very few temporal changes. Agricultural environments, on the other hand, are subject to seasonal changes, with plants varying in size and colours, offering less stable localisation features than buildings and road infrastructures, for example the author in Shalal et al. (2015) used the tree trunks of an orchard to improve the localisation. For this reason, among others like repetitive structures, uneven terrain or different light and wind conditions, achieving long-term autonomy for robots in such environments is both a challenging and interesting research problem (Kunze et al., 2018).

Datasets play a fundamental role in many research projects, as they allow us to test methodologies more quickly and more repeatably than having to rely on robot data acquired in real time. Mapping and localisation algorithms have greatly benefited from datasets like the popular KITTI (Geiger et al., 2013), providing a benchmarking tool to measure progress in the field. However, the public datasets in the field of agriculture robotics, although increasing, are still very limited, especially when trying to incorporate the long-term aspect. Relatively few autonomous commercial robot systems are deployed in agriculture scenarios, which does not incentivise the introduction of common standards and benchmarks. Studying the impact of long-term changes in the environment on mapping and localisation algorithms is therefore very challenging. Usually agriculture environments present more unique and varied characteristics than the

FIGURE 1 Robot navigating in the vineyard during a data collection session in March (left) and June (right).

urban counterparts, for example varying in appearance depending on the crop, the location in the world, the time of the year or terrain unevenness. Motivated by this set of challenges, we collected a dataset on the Ktima Gerovassiliou vineyard (Greece) over an entire crop season, starting in March 2022 until September 2022. The key idea was to cover 5 adjacent vineyard corridors driving autonomously along the crop rows with the robot depicted in Figure 1. In each session the robot follows the same path in order to capture the changes in the environment over time, covering from a completely naked vine plant to a fully blossomed state, but also different light conditions and changes due to human intervention such as pruning or grass mowing (see Figure 1). The total collected data so far amounts to roughly 600 Gigabytes, with a total distance covered by the robot of 5.5 km and a total deployment time of 5.5 hours. It includes multimodal data captured by two cameras providing Red Green Blue and Depth (RGB-D) images, two 2d light detection and ranging (lidar) sensors, one 3d lidar and an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), together with navigation data comprising wheel odometry and ground truth based on real-time kinematics global navigation satellite system (RTK-GNSS).

As the main contribution of this manuscript, we present a dataset, which to the best of the authors' knowledge is the first long-term dataset in the agricultural domain with overlapping paths. Its primary objective is to push developments and evaluations of different mapping and localisation algorithms for long-term autonomous robots operating in agricultural fields, however, we believe that thanks to its temporal aspect, the dataset can also be used for phenotyping and crop mapping tasks (e.g. see Lu and Young (2020)). Besides the dataset, as a second contribution, we provide an initial evaluation of data gathered using a 3d lidar map-based localisation and a visual SLAM approach, focusing on the analysis of the localisation performance with the seasonal changes. The work presented here is an extension of the preliminary work present as a short paper in Polvara et al. (2022).

In the remainder of this manuscript, we assess the existing datasets in the literature relevant to long-term datasets in the agricultural domain, a description of the robot and the scenario set up, which data is recorded, how the data is stored and how it can be retrieved. We end up with the data evaluation and the discussion sections.

2 | RELATED WORK

There are many dataset in the literature that aim at localisation and mapping tasks, from indoor scenes (Lee et al., 2021) to outdoor urban (Blanco-Claraco et al., 2014) and rural (Pire et al., 2019) scenes. However, it is not common

for those to include the seasonal aspect, making them useless when trying to tackle the challenges arising from the long-term temporal changes in the environment. Furthermore, when trying to combine long-term data with outdoor rural environments, like agriculture or forestry, even fewer datasets can be found, making the work presented in this document relevant for the community. In Table 1 we present a summary of the related datasets found in the literature. The summary is limited to the most relevant and recent works, with focus on the long-term mapping and localisation and/or in the agriculture domain for mapping applications. More comprehensive surveys in localisation and mapping algorithms used for different applications besides mapping such as navigation, precision agriculture and forestry SLAM, can be found in Aguiar et al. (2020); Ding et al. (2022).

Among the most popular datasets that include long-term data acquisition, we find the datasets NCLT, Oxford and Boreas. These are focused on urban environments and although they provide more than a year worth of recordings, the environment is completely different to having a robot navigating in a tree orchard or vineyard, so many mapping and localisation algorithms may perform very different (Shu et al., 2021). Also long-term, we have the FinnForest in the forestry domain and the Sugar Beet and AgScan3D in the agriculture domain. In FinnForest, authors acquired data in summer and winter seasons with a car, but the sensor suite is limited and mainly aimed at visual SLAM. The Sugar Beet dataset, probably the public dataset most related to ours in terms of data collected, the time span is roughly 3 months. And AgScan3D, the dataset most related to ours regarding the environment, offers data from vineyards from 2 different seasons, however the dataset was aimed at measuring canopy density, so it lacks the RTK-GNSS used in most works as the ground truth for the SLAM algorithms. Besides the Sugar Beet and AgScan3D datasets, other ones in the agricultural domain are the FieldSAFE and the Rosario, but they do not focus on the long-term perspective. They are recorded in 1 and 3 days respectively, which does not provide enough time for the environment to change significantly. Besides the aforementioned limitations in the agricultural datasets, we also found that all of them do not provide overlapping paths in every session like the NCLT or Oxford (urban), instead they focus on acquiring a wider array of scenes, with the aim of capturing a wider extent of challenging situations. Although this is a perfectly valid approach, this limits the usability from a long-term perspective, as each session cannot be spatio-temporally related to previous or future sessions. Our datasets attempts to fill the gaps in the literature by providing a multi-modal sensor suite covering all the main sensors used for SLAM tasks (Ding et al., 2022), with a ground truth based on a dual antenna RTK-GNSS for absolute position and heading, and a long-term data acquisition with overlapping paths.

3 | DATA COLLECTION

3.1 | Robot Platform - Thorvald

The core robotic platform employed in this work is Thorvald - a modular, general purpose, lightweight and flexible robotic system designed to address multiple applications of field robotics in agricultural environments (Grimstad and From, 2017). The system consists of a set of re-configurable modules which can be combined freely to create robots of varying sizes and with varying kinematic properties suitable for particular task. To support the data collection process, we use a four-wheel drive and steer (4WD4S) wheel setup with a base length and width configuration of 1.5 and 1 m respectively so it can fit and navigate within a vineyard corridor. The robot's battery provides roughly 8 hours of autonomy without payload. The robot is controlled through a built-in computer running Linux (Ubuntu 18.04 LTS) and Robot Operating System (ROS Melodic).

TABLE 1 List and comparison of related datasets in the literature.

Dataset		Scenario					Sensors						
Name	Reference	Environment	Sessions	Overlapping	Length [†] [km]	Time span	RTK-GNSS	3d lidar	2d lidar	IMU	RGB	Depth	Wheel odom
NCLT	Carlevaris-Bianco et al. (2016)		27	Mix	5.5	15 mos	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	×	✓
Oxford	Maddern et al. (2017)		100	✓	10	20 mos	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	×
Boreas	Burnett et al. (2022)		44	✓	7.2	12 mos	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	×	×
Sugar Beet	Chebroly et al. (2017)		30	×	2.4	3 mos	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	✓
FieldSAFE	Kragh et al. (2017)		1	×	12	1 day	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	✓	×
FinnForest	Ali et al. (2020)		11	×	2.5	12 mos	✓	×	×	✓	✓	×	×
Rosario	Pire et al. (2019)		6	×	0.3	3 days	✓	×	×	✓	✓	✓	✓
AgScan3D	Lowe et al. (2021)		36	Mix	-	23 mos	× [‡]	✓	×	✓	×	×	×
Ours			11	✓	0.5	7 mos	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

[†]Per session ; [‡]Only standard GNSS used; Agricultural environment

TABLE 2 Sensors configuration during the data collection.

Sensor	Reference	Type	Resolution	FOV	Range	Rate
OS1-16	Ouster (2022)	3d lidar	H: 2048 points	360°	120 m	10 Hz
			V: 16 beams	33.2°		
Zed2	StereoLabs (2022)	RGB-D	RGB: 1920×1080	110°, 70°	N/A	15 fps
			D: 1920×1080			
MRS1000	SICK (2022)	2d lidar	1083 points	360°	50 m	20 Hz
RSX-UM7	RedshiftLabs (2022)	IMU	N/A	N/A	N/A	40 Hz
GNSS BX992	Trimble (2022)	RTK-GNSS	N/A	N/A	N/A	10 Hz

3.1.1 | Sensor setup

The robot is equipped with a multimodal sensor suite consisting of an RTK-GNSS (Trimble BX992), two RGB-D cameras (StereoLabs ZED2), one 3d lidar (OUSTER OS1-16), an IMU (RSX-UM7) and two 4-beams 2d lidars (SICK MRS1000) located at opposite corners of the robot. Figure 2 illustrate the location of all the sensors mounted on the platform and their frame of reference, Table 2 contains their specifications and configuration parameters and Table 3 defines their extrinsic parameters with respect to the robot reference frame placed in the center of robot at ground level (*base_link*).

FIGURE 2 Left: Robot sensor set up. Right: frame location for each sensor and the reference frame (*base_link*)

TABLE 3 Extrinsic parameters for the transformation from the robot's coordinate frame *base_link* to the frame of each sensor. The translation is given by x , y and z ; the rotation is given by the quaternion q .

Sensor	x [m]	y [m]	z [m]	q_x	q_y	q_z	q_w
OS1-16	-0.098	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000
Zed2 Front	0.345	0.060	0.763	0.000	0.017	0.000	1.000
Zed2 Side	-0.083	0.300	0.934	0.000	0.000	0.707	0.707
MRS1000 Front	0.706	0.492	0.616	0.000	0.000	0.387	0.922
MRS1000 Back	-0.706	-0.496	0.616	0.000	0.000	0.923	-0.385
RSX-UM7	-0.098	0.000	0.950	-1.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
GNSS BX992 Front	0.277	-0.310	1.394	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000
GNSS BX992 Back	-0.297	0.310	1.378	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.000

3.2 | Environment and campaign

In March of 2022, we started to conduct the long-term data acquisition campaign at Ktima Gerovassiliou vineyard. This vineyard extends for more than 100 ha located in the outskirts of Epanomi, Greece, however, for the data collection purposes we used 5 adjacent vineyard corridors close to the garage where the robot is usually stored (see Figure 3).

The objective was to collect data covering the whole season until the end of the harvesting process in order to capture the entire crops' growth. At the time of writing this manuscript, 11 sessions have been recorded so far in 2022: 23rd March, 6th and 20th April, 6th and 18th May, 1st, 8th, 22nd and 29th June, 13th July and 15th September. The data recording is happening at a different time intervals in order to accommodate a variable speed in the crop's growth stages, e.g., only one session has been performed in March, while four sessions (one week apart one from another) have been completed in June. This is because during winter the plants grow very slowly, not offering significant visual changes between consecutive weeks. On the other hand, in the warmest months of the year, the plants drastically change their aspect a few days apart. A comparison between how the plants look in March, April, May and June

FIGURE 3 Ktima Gerovassiliou vineyard and data collection area marked in yellow in the zoomed in right picture.

TABLE 4 Weather conditions during the days of the data recording sessions. Weather data from Thessaloniki Airport (16622) Weather Station, the closest to the vineyard location.

Date	Ave. Temp(°C)	Prec.(mm)	Press.(Hpa)	Wind sp.(km/h)	Cloud cover
23/03/2022	9.8	0	1025.4 Hpa	11	0/8
06/04/2022	11.9	0	1013.8 Hpa	10	2/8
20/04/2022	12.5	0	1014.1 Hpa	15	4/8
06/05/2022	16.1	0	1022.2 Hpa	9	6/8
18/05/2022	22.1	0.2	1014.2 Hpa	19	3/8
01/06/2022	25.1	0	1014.3 Hpa	10	2/8
08/06/2022	23.2	1.5	1010.2 Hpa	12	5/8
22/06/2022	28.2	0	1009.1 Hpa	6	2/8
29/06/2022	27	0	1014.7 Hpa	13	2/8
13/07/2022	25.2	0	1017.7 Hpa	16	2/8
15/09/2022	23.1	0	1013.3 Hpa	10	2/8

from the front ZED2 camera perspective can be seen in Figure 4. Furthermore, we provide in Table 4 the weather conditions for the days of the data acquisition.

Due to the long-term nature of the data collection process, one of the objectives was to make each data session acquisition as automated and as simple as possible to the user. To this end, we use the Topological Navigation Toolkit to enable autonomous navigation along all the corridors and we developed a Graphical User Interface (GUI) to ensure a smooth, reliable and repeatable data collection process every time a session had to be recorded. These two are described in the following sections.

3.3 | Topological autonomous navigation

Topological representations are often a key enabler for building real-world robotic system, as an underpinning concept to robot navigation. Blanco et al. (2008) is one of the earliest works on the hybrid topo-metric maps in robotics,

FIGURE 4 Different crop's growth stage starting from March to June. Frames taken from the front RGBD camera video stream.

which can be seen as on the foundations of the work presented. For the data collection, we use a topological representation as way to efficiently represent large-scale environments and as the unifying representation to facilitate the autonomous navigation of the robot platform. The code for defining, visualising and using such topological map and topological navigation is made publicly available to the community (L-CAS, 2022).

3.3.1 | Topological map

A topological map is a discrete representation that can be viewed as a tuple $M \rightarrow \langle N, E, A, R \rangle$, where N are the nodes representing physical locations in the Euclidean space, E are the edges which connects pair of nodes, A is the set of navigation actions that the robot can perform, and R is a set of Boolean conditions that are used to define restrictions to the robot navigation on the topology. The framework allows the robot to use any navigation action, which are implemented for different purposes, that can be performed on the topology.

A node $n \in N$ is itself a tuple $n \rightarrow \langle q, p, Z, P \rangle$, where $q \in \mathbb{R}^4$ is the orientation represented as a quaternion, $p \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the position in Euclidean space, Z is the set of Euclidean points outlining a polygon which defines the node's influence zone, and P is a logical predicate build from the atoms in R . Similarly, an edge $e \in E$ is a tuple $e \rightarrow \langle n_1, n_2, a, P \rangle$, where $n_1, n_2 \in N$ are the nodes connected by the edge e , $a \in A$ is the navigation action that the robot can perform in order to traverse e and P is a logical predicate build from the atoms in R . Each condition in R can be evaluated as true or false in real-time as well as the predicate, these can include for example any condition required for ensuring a proper navigation like checking a sensor is active or limiting edges to only one direction; if the predicate evaluates as false, the robot is not allowed to traverse the corresponding edge (or node).

An example of the topological map used for the data recording process can be seen in Figure 5a. The green arrows define the node pose (p, q), the red polygons around the nodes define the nodes' influence zone (Z), the lines between nodes define the edges (e) and the color of such edges define the action (a) which define the robot navigation behaviour between nodes. In our case the black edges, represent corridor traversal behaviour where the robot attempts to navigate in a straight line between the nodes and the white edges represent a corridor change action where the robot move sideways exploiting the omnidirectional robot configuration to efficiently change rows without complex manoeuvres.

3.3.2 | Topological path planning

An advantage of using topological representations in large scale environment like vineyards come from the path planning side. Finding a global path from the robot's current location to the goal location on a discrete topological map, considering restrictions on nodes and edges is computationally much more efficient that doing the same thing on a metric map of the same environment. Instead of using a traditional grid that could contain millions of cells, the global path planning in the topological map is based on the topological graph structure. We use the A^* search algorithm (Hart et al., 1968) using the Euclidean distance between nodes as the costs, in order to calculate the path in the graph structure between the node where the robot is currently located and the goal node. In case the robot is initialized outside of the topological structure, the robot would move to the closest topological node in the Euclidean space when the goal is sent.

For each session recorded, the robot traverses autonomously a human designed topological path (the same path for all the sessions) along the edges connecting the intermediates nodes. Taking Figure 5a as a reference, the path designed is: $B \rightarrow G \rightarrow F \rightarrow A \rightarrow B \rightarrow G \rightarrow H \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow I \rightarrow J \rightarrow E \rightarrow J \rightarrow I \rightarrow D \rightarrow C \rightarrow H \rightarrow G \rightarrow B$. This path makes first a full loop on the first 2 corridors enabling to test loop closure detections and then it proceeds to

(a) Topological map used for the navigation in the 5 corridors recorded.

(b) Example of the robot's path for a single session.

FIGURE 5 Topological map used for data collection and localisation output from a single session.

TABLE 5 Waypoints nodes coordinates.

Node name	Latitude	Longitude
A	40.4503109028	22.9242398399
B	40.4503008251	22.9242154257
C	40.4502963106	22.9241873023
D	40.4502871880	22.9241562716
E	40.4502820141	22.9241282246
F	40.4498599480	22.9243066652
G	40.4498567885	22.9242787728
H	40.4498573511	22.9242512733
I	40.4498510108	22.9242223272
J	40.4498528855	22.9241902421

cover each corridor twice, once in each direction, so that the side RGB-D camera can see all the vine rows from both sides. For completeness, in Table 5 we define the coordinates of the nodes corresponding to the main waypoints.

The length of this entire path is approximately 500 m, and it takes, on average, 25 min for the robot to complete it. The average robot speed during the traversal of a corridor is 0.6 m/s, while the robot speed is significantly lower for performing a row change operation.

3.3.3 | Topological localisation

The topological structure defined on the environment is essentially a discretization of the metric space where the robot is deployed. Hence, to localise the robot in the topological map, we can exploit the output from any off-the-shelf localisation module as the input to define the node where the robot is located or edge the robot is traversing. During the data collection, we used the *robot_localisation* package (Moore and Stouch, 2016) combining the wheel odometry and the RTK-GNSS, obtaining on average around 2-3 cm estimated localisation error. To incorporate the RTK-GNSS data into robot map coordinates, the same fixed Datum configuration is used for all the sessions: [latitude: 40.45025, longitude 22.9243, orientation: 0.0], which define the origin of the map coordinate frame. An example of the localisation output during a session for the whole path can be seen in Figure 5b.

3.4 | GUI-assisted deployment

In order to simplify the operation of the robot and make it more accessible also to inexperienced users, special desktop icons and a GUI were designed (Figure 6) for the robot onboard touch monitor. More specifically, two icons “Start Robot” and “Robot Stop” allows to launch and stop, respectively, the core functionalities of the platform, such as the *roscore*, the 2D lasers for obstacle detection, the RTK-GNSS for the localisation and the *topological_navigation* module for the navigation. The core functionality also includes launching the *ROBOT HEALTH* module to inform the user about the platform’s status. A red/green palette is used to communicate if a specific module/sensor is currently working or not. For example, in Figure 6 is possible to see how the 2D lasers icon is green meaning the lasers are correctly up and running. However, the GPS label is still red indicating either the GNSS driver is not running or the accuracy error

is above a certain threshold, so it is not safe for the operator to start the autonomous navigation and in case the robot is navigating, it is used to stop it automatically and wait until better reception. Other icons include the start/stop of the sensor suite (IMU, 3d lidar and two RGB-D cameras), the start/stop of the autonomous navigation following the path defined in Section 3.3.2 and the start/stop of the data recording script. Additionally, an instruction video was done to assist with the data collection procedure for any user, experienced or inexperienced (LCAS).

4 | DATA STORAGE AND QUERYING

Data is recorded and stored in a MongoDB database by using `topic_store` (TS) (Kirk, 2020). MongoDB is an open source, non relational database management system (DBMS) that uses flexible documents instead of tables and rows to process and store various forms of data. As a NoSQL solution, MongoDB does not require a relational database management system (RDBMS), so it provides an elastic data storage model that enables users to store and query multivariate data types with ease. MongoDB documents or collections of documents are the basic units of data. Formatted as Binary JSON (Java Script Object Notation), these documents can store several types of data and be distributed across multiple systems.

Unlike ROS bags, TS adds flexibility by serialising all the ROS messages into a data hierarchy that is easily searchable with database queries and allows for remote storage. The user simply needs to define a scenario file listing all the topics to record and the hierarchy to adopt. In our setup, we store the information from all the sensors (2d/3d lidars, RGB-D, RTK-GNSS and IMU), together with other navigation data such as odometry, current topological location, etc. In Table 6 we summarise all the ROS topics stored.

Data is stored and indexed locally and then synchronised with a remote server. This can be queried and inspected to retrieve data at a specific time and location. The most-user-friendly way to inspect the database is by using Mon-

FIGURE 6 Screenshot of the integrated robot screen showing the special icons and GUI designed to facilitate the interaction with the robot during the data collection process.

TABLE 6 Topics stored in each data session.

Sensor	Topic Name	ROS Message Type
Ouster OS-1	/os_cloud_node/points	sensor_msgs/PointCloud2
	/os_cloud_node/imu	sensor_msgs/Imu
	/os_cloud_node/imu_packets	ouster_ros/PacketMsg
Zed2 Front	/front/zed_node/atm_press	sensor_msgs/FluidPressure
	/front/zed_node/depth/camera_info	sensor_msgs/CameraInfo
	/front/zed_node/imu/data	sensor_msgs/Imu
	/front/zed_node/imu/mag	sensor_msgs/MagneticField
	/front/zed_node/odom	nav_msgs/Odometry
	/front/zed_node/path_map	nav_msgs/Path
	/front/zed_node/path_odom	nav_msgs/Path
	/front/zed_node/pose	geometry_msgs/PoseStamped
	/front/zed_node/pose_with_covariance	geometry_msgs/PoseWithCovarianceStamped
	/front/zed_node/rgb/camera_info	sensor_msgs/CameraInfo
	/front/zed_node/rgb/image_rect_color/compressed	sensor_msgs/CompressedImage
	/front/zed_node/temperature/imu	sensor_msgs/Temperature
	/front/zed_node/temperature/left	sensor_msgs/Temperature
	/front/zed_node/temperature/right	sensor_msgs/Temperature
	/depth_republish/compressedDepth	sensor_msgs/CompressedImage
Zed2 Side	/side/zed_node/atm_press	sensor_msgs/FluidPressure
	/side/zed_node/depth/camera_info	sensor_msgs/CameraInfo
	/side/zed_node/imu/data	sensor_msgs/Imu
	/side/zed_node/imu/mag	sensor_msgs/MagneticField
	/side/zed_node/odom	nav_msgs/Odometry
	/side/zed_node/path_map	nav_msgs/Path
	/side/zed_node/path_odom	nav_msgs/Path
	/side/zed_node/pose	geometry_msgs/PoseStamped
	/side/zed_node/pose_with_covariance	geometry_msgs/PoseWithCovarianceStamped
	/side/zed_node/rgb/camera_info	sensor_msgs/CameraInfo
	/side/zed_node/rgb/image_rect_color/compressed	sensor_msgs/CompressedImage
	/side/zed_node/temperature/imu	sensor_msgs/Temperature
	/side/zed_node/temperature/left	sensor_msgs/Temperature
	/side/zed_node/temperature/right	sensor_msgs/Temperature
	/depth_republish_2/compressedDepth	sensor_msgs/CompressedImage
RSX-UM7	/imu/data	sensor_msgs/Imu
	/imu/mag	geometry_msgs/Vector3Stamped
	/imu/rpy	geometry_msgs/Vector3Stamped
MSR1000	/scan	sensor_msgs/LaserScan
	/merged_cloud	sensor_msgs/LaserScan
RTK-GNSS	/gps/filtered	sensor_msgs/NavSatFix
	/gps/fix	sensor_msgs/NavSatFix
	/health/gps/error_std	std_msgs/Float64
Other	/odometry/base_raw	nav_msgs/Odometry
	/odometry/gps	nav_msgs/Odometry
	/odometry/gps/unfiltered	nav_msgs/Odometry
	/robot_pose	geometry_msgs/Pose
	/yaw	sensor_msgs/Imu
	/current_node	std_msgs/String
	/closest_node	std_msgs/String
	/tf	tf2_msgs/TFMessage
	/tf_static	tf2_msgs/TFMessage
	/time_reference	sensor_msgs/TimeReference

FIGURE 7 Overview of MongoDB Compass for inspecting the data collected during the recording session.

godb *Compass* and establishing a working connection to the database itself.

Once the connection to the server has been established, it is possible to have access to all the databases and their respective collections. By selecting “kg_recording” we can have an overview of the documents that have been created during the data collection session, as seen in Figure 7. Each document has the same hierarchical structure defined in the TS scenario file.

4.1 | Database connection

To connect to the remote server hosting the data collected across all the recording sessions, a generic user needs first to define a few environmental variables such as the database’s and collection’s name but also the user credentials. A dedicated script allows extracting data from the remote database in the format of a ROS bag. In order to do so, a user needs, first of all, to define a particular query so as to filter only a portion of data. For example, a user would be interested to extract only a specific recording session out of the complete set of data. Hence, after having identified the *ObjectId* of the session they are interested in (e.g. 23032022), they can type in the command line the following:

```
roslaunch topic_store convert.py
-i "mongodb://$MONGouser:$MONGOPASS@files.lar.lincoln.ac.uk:8098/?authSource=bacchus&tls=true&tlsInsecure=true"
-c kg_recording
-q '{"_ts_meta.session": "ObjectId(23032022)"}'
-o session_23032022.bag
```

One can also add a projection (-p) to select which fields should be extracted (e.g., only the laser data). More information about other parameters can be found in the Topic Store wiki (Kirk, 2020).

FIGURE 8 Pipeline followed for the localisation evaluation.

5 | DATA EVALUATION

The final objective of the data collection is to create a dataset of robot sensor data that can be useful for developing and benchmarking novel mapping and localisation algorithms in the agricultural domain. An interesting research question to address is about the long-term deployment of a robot in an environment that is subject to seasonal changes, offering severe challenges for what concerns the robot's localisation in such an environment. Within this scope, we are providing in this manuscript a comparison performed using data from four different data recording sessions. To be specific, the sessions recorded the 23rd March 2022, 6th April 2022, 6th May 2022, and 8th June 2022, the same from which we extracted the frames shown in Figure 4. The goal of this study is to quantify if and how the localisation performance varies over time when trying to localise the robot using a map built in a different moment, e.g., the robot aims at localising itself in April while using a map built in March.

As a testbed, we assessed the robot traversing the first two corridors of the research area at Ktima Gerovassiliou. More specifically, the robot starts at the beginning of the second corridor, which is traversed entirely, and then returns using the first corridor before traversing the second corridor again, completing a loop. Taking as reference Figure 5, the path is $B \rightarrow G \rightarrow F \rightarrow A \rightarrow B \rightarrow G$, which correspond to the first 150 meters from the total 500 m a full session has.

For the whole evaluation process, we follow a 3-step pipeline as shown in Figure 8, consisting of mapping, localisation, and evaluation. Before the 3d lidar point cloud is fed in the FAST-LIO (Xu and Zhang, 2021) mapping and the NDT-Localiser (Magnusson, 2009) algorithms, a people remover filter step is applied to the raw points. For safety reasons, during the recording process, a person was always following the robot some meters behind in case an emergency stop must be triggered. So, in order to remove the person, a 3d area behind the robot is cropped out of all the scans using the PCL filter library.

5.1 | 3d Mapping

As the first step in the pipeline, we initially create a 3d map using FAST-LIO (Fast lidar-Inertial Odometry). This uses as input the point cloud data from the Ouster OS-1 3d lidar mounted on top of the robot and its IMU data. FAST-LIO is a computationally efficient and robust lidar-inertial odometry package. It fuses lidar feature points with IMU data using a tightly coupled iterated extended Kalman filter to allow robust navigation in fast-motion, noisy or cluttered environments where degeneration occurs. The resulting output is a 3d point cloud that can be stored in *pcd* format.

A visual representation of the 4 maps obtained using FAST-LIO for the four sessions is offered in Figure 9. Moving

from late winter across spring and into summer, poles disappear from the map because the plants are now covered by leaves, which also occlude lidar beams preventing mapping more of the surrounding environment.

5.2 | Localisation

The resulting maps are then used for localising the robot using a method based on the Normal Distribution Transform (NDT), which tries to match each point cloud obtained by the 3d lidar with the pre-built map. However, this technique does not try to match the current lidar scan to points in the map; instead, it tries to match points from the current scan to a 3d grid of probability functions created from the map. The probability distributions are obtained by dividing the point cloud into a uniform 3d grid where each 3d cell (voxel) contains the mean and standard deviation of the points belonging to it, representing a normal distribution. This way, even if the robot measures a point a few millimetres away from where the map thinks a point should be, instead of being completely unable to match those two points, the NDT matching function connects the measured point to the probability function on the map.

There are 3 factors worth mentioning which affect the performance of the NDT localiser: (i) the down-sampling method of the input point cloud (voxel grid filter), (ii) the resolution of the point cloud map, and (iii) the initial pose given to the robot at the beginning of the process. Regarding (i), all the points present in each voxel of the input voxel grid will be approximated (i.e., down-sampled) with their centroid. This approach is a bit slower than approximating them with the centre of the voxel, but it represents the underlying surface more accurately. An experimental analysis found that a leaf (voxel side's length) of 0.1 m offers the best trade-off between computational efficiency and properly capturing salient features in the map, such as leaves and crops. The resolution parameter (ii) defines the voxel resolution of the internal NDT grid structure used for representing the environmental map. This structure is easily searchable, and each voxel contains the statistical data (e.g., mean and covariance) associated with the points it contains. The statistical data is used to model the cloud as a set of multivariate Gaussian distributions and allows us to calculate and optimise the probability of the existence of points at any position within the voxel. This parameter needs to be large enough for each voxel to contain at least six points but small enough to uniquely describe the environment. For this reason, we found a value of 2.0 to work for our setting. Finally, for what concerns the initial pose of the robot (iii), in all the experiments we set it to be the same from which the mapping task has started, so as to facilitate the initial localisation of the robot itself. In fact, all the temporal snapshots have been extracted from the database by filtering for the same starting position (in GNSS coordinates) so as to spatially align them in an easy way.

5.3 | Evaluation

In order to evaluate the NDT localiser performance, we compare the output produced as estimated odometry against the pose given by the RTK-GNSS. We define a grid-matrix experiment in which, for every month's map, we compute the localisation error for every dataset time-snapshot. The estimated average localisation error present in the RTK-GNSS pose used as a ground truth is: 0.038 m, 0.008 m, 0.044 m and 0.010 m for the March, April, May and June sessions respectively.

5.3.1 | Metrics

Following the current trends in robotic localisation literature, the metrics we adopted for evaluating the localisation error are the Absolute Pose Error (APE) (Lu and Milios, 1997), the Relative Pose Error (RPE) and the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). The Evo (Grupp, 2017) library has been used for computing the metrics and comparing the resulting

FIGURE 9 Point cloud map and zoomed-in detail of the testing area built by FAST-LIO out of the data recorded from March 2022 to June 2022. The points associated with the ground have been removed to make the visualisation clearer. It is possible to see how the point cloud in March and April looks almost the same due to the fact that the plants are still in a dormant stage, with no leaves or branches. Only the vertical poles and the horizontal water pipe are present in these two time snapshots.

trajectories.

APE

Corresponding poses are directly compared between estimate and reference, given a pose relation. Then, statistics for the whole trajectory are calculated. This is useful to test the global consistency of a trajectory. APE is based on the absolute relative pose between two poses $P_{est,i}, P_{ref,i} \in SE(3)$ at timestamp i :

$$E_i = P_{est,i} \ominus P_{ref,i} = P_{ref,i}^{-1} P_{est,i} \in SE(3) \quad (1)$$

Where \ominus is the inverse composition operator, which takes two poses and gives the relative pose. Different pose relations can be used to calculate the APE, such as only translation, only rotation, or the full transformation:

$$APE_i = \| E_i - I_{4 \times 4} \|_F \quad (2)$$

RPE

The relative poses along the estimated and the reference trajectory are compared. This is based on the delta pose difference. This metric gives insights into the local accuracy, i.e., the drift.

$$E_{i,j} = \delta_{est,i,j} \ominus \delta_{ref,i,j} = (P_{ref,i}^{-1} P_{ref,j})(P_{est,i}^{-1} P_{est,j}) \in SE(3) \quad (3)$$

It is possible to use different pose relations to calculate the RPE from timestamp i to j . For example, if we want to consider the full transformation as before:

$$RPE_{i,j} = \| E_{i,j} - I_{4 \times 4} \|_F \quad (4)$$

RMSE

Different statistics can be calculated on the APEs and RPEs of all timestamps, among them, the RMSE:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{ij} APE_{i,j}^2} \quad (5)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{ij} RPE_{i,j}^2} \quad (6)$$

5.3.2 | Results

The results are reported in Table 7 and Table 8 for the APE and the RPE, respectively. It is possible to see how, in general, the localisation error grows in those situations in which the map and the dataset time snapshot used belong to different months. For example, the first row of Table 7 shows that, while localising on the map built in March, the localisation error for May (0.35) and June (0.44) is bigger than the one for March and April (which are comparable – 0.30). More specifically, as expected, it can be noted that usually the smallest error is located on the main diagonal of

TABLE 7 Absolute Pose Error (APE – expressed as mean and standard deviation) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) while cross-testing the NDT Localiser on seasonal data. Best result in bold.

	SNAPSHOT	March		April		May		June	
		APE	RMSE	APE	RMSE	APE	RMSE	APE	RMSE
MAP	March	0.31(0.17)	0.36	0.29(0.18)	0.35	0.35(0.20)	0.40	0.44(0.22)	0.49
	April	0.51(0.29)	0.59	0.37(0.19)	0.42	0.39(0.20)	0.44	0.50(0.52)	0.72
	May	0.40(0.31)	0.51	0.41(0.16)	0.43	0.24(0.21)	0.32	0.23(0.43)	0.48
	June	Fail		Fail		0.22(0.08)	0.25	0.16(0.07)	0.17

TABLE 8 Relative Pose Error (RPE – expressed as mean and standard deviation) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) while cross-testing the NDT Localiser on seasonal data. Best result in bold.

	SNAPSHOT	March		April		May		June	
		RPE	RMSE	RPE	RMSE	RPE	RMSE	RPE	RMSE
MAP	March	0.03(0.01)	0.12	0.03(0.03)	0.04	0.03(0.06)	0.07	0.05(0.06)	0.08
	April	0.04(0.14)	0.14	0.02(0.06)	0.07	0.03(0.02)	0.04	0.06(0.16)	0.17
	May	0.05(0.19)	0.19	0.03(0.02)	0.03	0.05(0.02)	0.03	0.05(0.33)	0.34
	June	Fail		Fail		0.03(0.07)	0.08	0.03(0.04)	0.05

the resulting matrix, meaning that localising on the map built out of the same time snapshot always leads to better performance. In other words, localising on a map built in the same month in which the robot is deployed (or around the same date) achieves the lowest localisation error.

The most interesting result obtained is that testing the dataset time slice belonging to the March and April sessions on the summer map of June does fail to the point that metrics could not be computed. An intuitive explanation of such failure is that the sensor readings in March and April are quite sparse because the vines are still in a “dormant” stage and no foliage is present on them. Therefore, the only features present in the point cloud belong to the buildings and the structure which is located far from the robot. However, these features are not present in June’s map due to occlusions. In fact, during the summer months, the crops are in a growth stage so advanced that almost prevents any laser beam to leave the row in which the robot is located, impacting the mapping quality of the surrounding area.

5.4 | Adding Long-Term Stability Mapping

5.4.1 | 3d Long-Term Mapping

Capturing only the stable features in a given environment is the essence of enabling long-term operation. With this objective in mind, we propose LTS-Net (work currently under review), an end-to-end self-supervised learning model. The approach is data-driven and learns implicitly the long-term stable features by means of a neural network based on PointNet++ (Qi et al., 2017). The training data is generated in an unsupervised way by having multiple observations of the same environment taken at different times, and producing pointwise labelling representing each point’s long-term stability. The network is a regression model trained by using the stability score as a training signal. This approach was initially evaluated in the NCLT dataset (Carlevaris-Bianco et al., 2016), which provides data over multiple months. The

TABLE 9 Absolute Pose Error (APE – expressed as mean and standard deviation) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) while cross testing the NDT Localiser on seasonal data and map cleaned by LTS-Net. Best result in bold.

	SNAPSHOT	March		April		May		June	
		APE	RMSE	APE	RMSE	APE	RMSE	APE	RMSE
MAP	June	Fail		Fail		0.22(0.08)	0.25	0.16(0.07)	0.17
	June-filtered	Fail	0.16(0.06)	0.17		0.20(0.05)	0.21	0.07(0.04)	0.08

TABLE 10 Relative Pose Error (RPE – expressed as mean and standard deviation) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) while cross testing the NDT Localiser on seasonal data and map cleaned by LTS-Net. Best result in bold.

	SNAPSHOT	March		April		May		June	
		RPE	RMSE	RPE	RMSE	RPE	RMSE	RPE	RMSE
MAP	June	Fail		Fail		0.03(0.07)	0.08	0.03(0.04)	0.05
	June-filtered	Fail	0.02(0.03)	0.04		0.02(0.02)	0.03	0.04(0.05)	0.06

results showed that the network is able to implicitly learn the long-term stable features of that dataset. However, the nature of the NCTL dataset, collected inside a university campus and characterised by a large number of temporally stable features such as buildings and street lamps, offers limited possibilities to learn the long-term stability compared to the dataset we are proposing.

Therefore, we repeat the same experiment done in the previous section using the map from June after being filtered of the unstable points by using the target signal which LTS-Net is trained with, i.e. the LTS-Net module takes the output from the FAST-LIO mapping and filters it before providing it to the NDT localiser in Step 2 (see the updated pipeline in Figure 10). A visual comparison of the original map against the ground-truth filtered one is presented in Figure 11 (the ground points have been removed for clarity). The results of the experiments are reported in Table 9 and Table 10, in which we also report the metrics obtained using the original map to facilitate the comparison.

This final experiment shows that, by removing the temporally unstable points, is now possible to localise the robot in April while using June's map, with a discretely low error too (0.16). This validates the idea that, out of a point cloud map, LTS-Net can extract only those points which belong to stable temporal features such as poles and trunks, which are also the only features present in April's snapshot. Interestingly, also the localisation's performance while using the dataset snapshot of May and June has seen a consistent improvement: more specifically, the APE for June drastically dropped from 0.16 to 0.07.

FIGURE 10 Evaluation pipeline with the introduction of the LTS-Net.

FIGURE 11 Visual comparison of stable (blue) and unstable (green to red) features in the map built out of the data recording session of June before (left) and after (right) the filtering performed by LTS-Net.

Besides the increased localisation performance, another important advantage brought by LTS-Net is the possibility to reduce the number of maps the robot needs to build before being deployed autonomously. This is a crucial aspect when targeting outdoor robotic applications, in particular navigating an orchard which can extend for multiple square kilometres, making mapping a tedious and expensive task. In our experiments, we found that out of the four maps used, having only two maps (e.g., March and June) would be sufficient for achieving a precise localisation across four months. This is already a positive result because guarantees there is no need for mapping the vineyard every time the robot needs to be used for data collection or inspection. In addition, we showed that LST-Net can come in handy in extracting only those features which are stable across time (such as poles and trunks), removing from the map those points belonging to grass and leaves. In this way, it is possible not only to improve the localisation accuracy in general but to further extend the time required between two mapping sessions, with a saving in time and cost. Unfortunately, we noted that it was impossible to achieve a successful localisation in March while using a map built in June. Hence, future directions of this work will be towards improving the feature extraction capabilities of LTS-Net by also integrating the additional data that is planned to be recorded until the end of the next harvesting season.

5.4.2 | Visual Long-Term Stability

Another approach to the problem at hand is the use of visual features located in seasonally unchanged parts of the vineyard. To this end, on top of the previously described method, we evaluate our existing work (Papadimitriou et al., 2022) with data captured in the same region of the vineyard using the same APE, RPE and RMSE metrics. In Papadimitriou et al. (2022), we verified that focusing on salient features, which arise from the trunk regions of the vine trees, can improve place recognition performance. This work showcased a visual Graph-SLAM approach with a loop closure detection (LCD) strategy enforced by the instance segmentation of trunk regions. In this manuscript, we

are interested in the LCD methodology of the aforementioned work which we will describe in brief.

The pipeline focuses on the generation of a pool of salient visual features that uniquely characterises a scene across time, annotated as a Bag of Visual Words (BoVW), which are later used for LCD and optimisation of the graph. Specifically, as the robot moves inside a corridor, new nodes are added to a pose-graph, where each node represents the current robot pose. Each node is also associated with an RGB image of the robot's front camera which is used to generate the visual word (VW) of the scene. The VW generation relies on the instance segmentation of the scene to isolate the vine trunks. To this end, the Mask R-CNN network (He et al., 2017) has been selected and when a node is to be added in the graph, the instance segmentation model is triggered and processed to create an image with the isolated trunk regions, i.e., the trunks' mask. On this image, ORB features are calculated, the descriptor of which represents the VW. This process is depicted in Figure 12. The BoVW is formulated by the accumulation of the individual VWs and can be searched in a probabilistic manner to detect loop closures and localise the robot in the pose-graph. The pipeline is summarised in Figure 13.

FIGURE 12 The visual words computation pipeline: a) The original RGB image; b) The trunks binary mask; c) The extracted RGB trunks from the original image; d) The calculated ORB features on the trunks' mask.

FIGURE 13 The semantic segmentation of the scene and the probabilistic loop closure detection pipeline.

For completeness, we evaluate the described methodology with the metrics described in Section 5.3.1 on a dataset created in the same part of the vineyard region as the dataset described in Section 5. Two experiments were performed during June on two different corridors of the vineyard. The experiments are annotated as EX01 and EX02 for convenience. The path followed by the robot was the $A \rightarrow F \rightarrow G \rightarrow B \rightarrow A \rightarrow F$ and the $D \rightarrow I \rightarrow J \rightarrow E \rightarrow D \rightarrow I$ for EX01 and EX02 respectively (see Figure 5a). The results are shown in Table 11.

TABLE 11 Evaluation of the Graph-SLAM methodology in terms of APE and RPE expressed as Mean and Standard Deviation (STD) and the respective Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). Units in meters.

Experiment	APE		RPE	
	Mean(STD)	RMSE	Mean(STD)	RMSE
EX01	0.65(0.32)	0.72	0.77(0.36)	0.85
EX02	0.54(0.22)	0.58	0.71(0.35)	0.62

While the metrics do not outperform the LTS-Net methodology, it is worth mentioning that the algorithm correctly classified more than 50% of the existing loop closures in both experiments. This indicates that the presented LCD scheme can be utilised as a place recognition algorithm by tackling the uniformity of the vineyard environment. As future work, we are focusing on the exploitation of this scheme to achieve consistent long-term localisation based on visual features.

6 | DISCUSSION

By means of a robust and reproducible data recording pipeline, we have presented as the main contribution of this manuscript the Bacchus Long-Term Dataset or BLT in short. Long-term deployment of an autonomous robot in agricultural environments such as a vineyard arises many challenges in localisation and mapping tasks. These challenges come from different sources such as an ever-lasting changing environment, uneven terrain, different weather conditions or sudden man-made changes. Hence, with the proposed dataset we attempt to create an appealing framework that the robotics community can use to benchmark their mapping and localisation methods under such challenging conditions.

To support multiple approaches, the BLT dataset contains data from a complete suite of sensors, including 3d lidar, 2d lidar, RGB-D camera, IMU and RTK-GNSS for ground truth, recorded for a 7-month period in the same vineyard area. The data acquisition started in March 2022 and ended in September 2022 for a total of 11 sessions, however, the plan is to continue the data recording during at least another season. In this way, a long-term analysis can be performed on the different methodologies of what a long-term deployment of a robot in such an environment would implicate. Following this line of discussion and to show the usefulness of the data gathered, as a second contribution we have evaluated state-of-the-art algorithms using four sessions of our dataset and demonstrated they can only deal with relatively low temporal changes in plants and crops. The localisation performance drops as time passes and the environment changes due to the nature of the seasonal plant growth. As a way to overcome this issue, we introduced a long-term stability mapping discussion with two approaches (3d lidar-based and visual-based) which, according to the preliminary results obtained, can improve the localisation error and reduce the frequency at which new maps must be created for guaranteeing a correct and efficient deployment of the robotic platform. However, our study is far away from addressing the problem completely, hence we invite the robotics community to use our dataset

for benchmarking their methods. Future work is aimed at creating an automated submission system with the results of different algorithms and enhancing the dataset with other annotations. For example, crop mapping annotations covering multiple grape stages could be interesting so that the dataset can be also appealing to other machine vision communities.

Finally, to wrap up the discussion, we would like to report on the lessons learned and challenges faced during the robot setup, deployment and data collection. Since the idea from the beginning was to record data in a frequent basis, we wanted that the data recording process was as streamlined as possible, with as low as possible human intervention and that error sources were easy to spot even for inexperienced robot users. This is key since time in agricultural fields or other outdoor environments is always difficult to coordinate, takes extra effort (e.g. travelling times to the vineyard) or the weather conditions are quite often not great from the human perspective. With our pipeline and the GUI developed that reports feedback in real-time, only 35 minutes were needed to record a 30-minute session, with human intervention reduced to only taking the robot in and out of the garage and pressing a couple of buttons to start and stop the recording. All this enabled frictionless support by the different people involved in the data collection process. Regarding the robot navigation, we found that using the topological navigation, although being a bit less flexible in terms of robot manoeuvring capabilities compared to a default ROS *move_base* configuration or simply a teleoperation by the user, offered a more reliable, consistent and deterministic navigation approach around the field. As a consequence, we could also obtain more consistent data collection sessions that can be more easily compared between them as the robot follows very similar paths. The user still needed to check that there were for example no massive holes in the path, but the navigation, although supervised, was completely autonomous. And last but not least, from the pure data collection point of view, a challenge we faced was the bandwidth needed to acquire and save all the data coming from all the sensors, especially when multiple RGB-D cameras are involved. More specifically, we identified a weakness in the single-thread compression and writing performance of the ROS *bag* tool, especially when dealing with four streams (two RGB and two depth) of high-resolution images. Even when using a high-performance Non-Volatile Memory Express (NVMe) disk and compressing images with the ROS *image_transport* package, we noticed that the ROS *bag* was not able to write on the disk in real time, leading to data corruption and wrong time stamps. Motivated by these problems, we designed and implemented *topic_store* which proved to be an invaluable asset during our data recording pipeline.

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